

Data Type Registry Governance Model

	Name	Partner/Activity	Date
From:	Hans Lienhop	GWDG	25.05.2025

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1. Introduction

The Data Type Registry (DTR) Governance Model is designed to ensure transparent, sustainable, and FAIR-compliant management of data types while using the Data Type Registry established in the FAIRCORE4EOSC project. It aligns with the project's objectives of fostering interoperability, openness, and responsible data stewardship.

2. General Governance Principles

The DTR operates as an open infrastructure that upholds the FAIR data principles. It provides a platform where users can register, propose, share, and adopt data types in accordance with established standards. Oversight is provided by a committee of experts to ensure all activities are in alignment with broader strategies.

3. Access and Usage Policies

3.1 DTR Instances

The Gesellschaft für Wissenschaftliche Datenverarbeitung Göttingen mbH (GWDG) maintains both a test and a production instance of the DTR under ePIC¹ stewardship. The test instance is open to users for experimentation and creation of new data types. Each newly created type is assigned a unique identifier. In contrast, the production instance houses a carefully curated and validated collection of types. GWDG supports a federated environment that encompasses multiple DTR instances and enables federated search and additional functionalities. Admission into this federation requires committee approval and adherence to the DTR Interoperability Guidelines.

3.2 User Access

User access to the test instance is facilitated through EOSC AAI, the Academic Cloud, or manual administrative approval. The production instance grants write access only to a designated expert committee, while read access is available to the general public.

4. Hosting and Deployment

Users have the ability to host their own DTR instances using publicly available schemas². Only those instances that have been validated and approved are eligible for integration into the official federated service. The DTR's open-source nature allows users to fork and modify its codebase, provided they adhere to the applicable open-source licensing terms. Any use of a hosted instance as a commercial service must also comply with the software's licensing agreements.

¹ <https://www.pidconsortium.net/>

² <https://github.com/FC4E-T4-3/schemas>

5. Curation and Approval Processes

5.1 Type Promotion Process

Users may submit their data types for consideration in the production instance. These submissions are evaluated periodically by a panel of domain experts. Upon approval, the data types are incorporated into the production environment and assigned new persistent identifiers following a consensus decision-making process.

5.2 Type Modification and Deletion

Modifications to existing types within the production instance can only be carried out through a formal review process. To manage outdated types, a deprecation procedure will be introduced, ensuring continuity and traceability. Users may propose changes or suggest new features via an official request system.

6. Governance Committee and Decision-Making

A governance committee composed of domain specialists oversees all policy decisions related to the DTR. The committee conducts regular reviews to maintain alignment with evolving FAIR, EOSC and ePIC standards. Additionally, mechanisms are in place to resolve any disputes that may arise concerning data type definitions.

7. Compliance and Security

To ensure equitable use and prevent abuse, API access may be subject to rate limits. Access privileges can be revoked in cases of misuse, policy violations, or security threats. The governance framework also ensures compliance with the data protection regulations of EOSC member states, including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

8. Sustainability and Future Development

The governance model of the DTR is designed to evolve based on ongoing community feedback and technological developments. Funding mechanisms and strategies for long-term sustainability will be reviewed on a regular basis. Additionally, the expansion of federated functionalities will be explored to facilitate broader adoption.